

Status of the International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project

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ABSTRACT

The International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) has continued its work generating evaluations of new and historical benchmark experiments since the 2024 Physics of Reactors (PHYSOR) Conference. Two additional editions of the ICSBEP Handbook have been published since that update, and the Technical Review Group (TRG) held two in-person meetings to review and approve additional benchmarks. The 2022 and 2023 editions of the Handbook were combined into one release (published in November 2024) and contained 13 new evaluations with 46 different configurations and two major revisions to existing evaluations. The 2024 version of the Handbook contains two new evaluations with 15 new configurations and one major revision to HEU-MET-FAST-028, the evaluation of Flattop with a uranium core. The 2025 version of the Handbook, currently undergoing final editing, will contain eight new evaluations with 25 new configurations, including 19 critical cases, two shielding cases, and four new fundamental physics configurations. The ICSBEP TRG will meet again in person in April 2026 to review benchmarks for the 2026 ICSBEP Handbook. Many of the new benchmarks represent contemporaneous experiments that have been specifically targeted to address long-standing gaps in the ICSBEP benchmark set. One major area of focus for new critical experiments is to target the sparsely populated intermediate energy (or resonance) region. Another focus of many of the new benchmarks is to provide experiments sensitive to materials that would interest the advanced reactor community, such as chlorine, hafnium, tantalum, copper, molybdenum, and graphite. The ICSBEP continues to deliver high-quality, peer reviewed evaluations of integral experiments relevant to the nuclear criticality safety, reactor physics, and nuclear data communities.

Keywords: ICSBEP, Integral Experiments, Critical Experiments, Benchmarks, validation

1. INTRODUCTION

The International Criticality Safety Benchmark Evaluation Project (ICSBEP) and its associated Handbook [1] of evaluated benchmark experiments is the premiere source of trusted benchmarks for criticality safety calculation and nuclear data validation worldwide. The ICSBEP is an official activity of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA), which coordinates the Technical Review Group (TRG) participation amongst NEA member countries and publishes the Handbook. The Handbook represents the technical contributions from hundreds of dedicated individuals from 28 different countries over a 30-year period.

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Since the last Physics of Reactors (PHYSOR) Conference in 2024, two additional editions of the ICSBEP Handbook have been published. The 2022/2023 Handbook edition was released in November 2024 and was a combined release representing two years of evaluation, review, and approval and included 13 new evaluations with a total of 42 new configurations. Two evaluations underwent major revisions. In late 2025, the 2024 edition of the Handbook was published, with two new evaluations and one major revision to an existing evaluation included. All revised and new evaluations published in the 2022/2023 and 2024 editions of the handbook are further described in Sections 2 and 3 of this paper.

The TRG met in April of 2025 in Ljubljana, Slovenia, to review benchmarks for inclusion in the 2025 ICSBEP Handbook. Eight new evaluations were finalized for publication from that meeting, and the 2025 edition of the handbook is currently undergoing final editing. An overview of the 2025 evaluations is provided in Section 4 of this paper.

2. NEW EVALUATIONS

The 2022/2023 and 2024 editions of the Handbooks contain a total of 15 new evaluations representing 53 different experimental benchmark configurations. A summary of the new 2022/2023 Handbook contents and the total Handbook contents are provided in Table I.

Table I: New and Total Contents of the 2022/2023 and 2024 ICSBEP Handbook Editions

ICSBEP Type	New Configurations for 2022/2023 and 2024	Total Configurations in Handbook
PU	7	805
HEU	22	1459
IEU	4	278
LEU	11	1827
U233	0	244
MIX (Pu/U)	0	536
SPEC (Other Actinides)	0	20
ALARM (Shielding)	4	51
FUND (Physics)	5	242

2.1. New Plutonium Evaluations

Two new plutonium (Pu) evaluations were added to the Handbook. Descriptions of the new Pu evaluations are provided, below.

PU-MET-THERM-004: This experiment was the third in the Thermal Epithermal eXperiments (TEX) series, a collaboration between Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) and Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), using Zero Power Physics Reactor (ZPPR) plutonium/aluminum alloy plates. This TEX-Pu variant, completed at the National Criticality Experiments Research Center (NCERC), was designed with thick polyethylene and polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA, or Lucite) moderators to be sensitive to thermal scattering laws [2]. Two thicknesses of each moderator were used for a total of four configurations.

PU-MET-THERM-005: This experiment, the Chlorine Worth Study, was designed to provide a validation case for various concentrations of Pu chloride solutions [3]. The experiment was conducted by LANL at NCERC with stacks of plutonium/aluminum alloy ZPPR plates, polyethylene moderators, and polyvinyl chloride or chlorinated polyvinyl chloride absorber plates. Three configurations, each targeting a different concentration of Pu chloride solution, were evaluated.

2.2. New Highly Enriched Uranium Evaluations

Five new highly enriched uranium (HEU) evaluations were added to the 2022/2023 Handbook. Descriptions of the new HEU evaluations are provided, below.

HEU-MET-FAST-102: This experiment was a collaboration between the Japan Atomic Energy Agency (JAEA) and LANL to test the void reactivity worth for lead for fast reactors. Thin HEU Jemima plates were stacked with interstitial lead, reflected by the Zeus copper, and measured on Comet at NCERC [4]. Three experiments were evaluated, one being a reference configuration and the other two with increasing lead void via the implementation of aluminum spacers.

HEU-MET-FAST-104: This benchmark evaluates the critical configurations for the LANL Measurement of Uranium Subcritical and Critical (MUSIC) experiments, which measured a range of subcritical and critical configurations of bare HEU nesting shells on the Planet machine at NCERC [5]. The goal of this experiment was to produce a modern, high precision bare HEU benchmark. Evaluation of the subcritical configurations as fundamental physics benchmarks are planned for the future.

HEU-MET-INTER-011: The LANL Critical Unresolved Region Integral Experiment (CURIE) was performed on Comet using the Zeus copper reflector at NCERC. It was designed to provide a test for nuclear data in the ^{235}U unresolved resonance region (URR) [4]. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, or Teflon) was used as an interstitial material between the Jemima plates to slightly moderate the neutrons into the URR and thus also provides a test for fluorine nuclear data in this energy region.

HEU-MET-INTER-013 (also cross listed as HEU-MET-FAST-105, HEU-MET-MIXED-022, and HEU-MET-THERM-037): This benchmark evaluates the second series of TEX-HEU experiments performed on the Comet machine at NCERC. This series introduced hafnium plates as an interstitial diluent to the experimental stacks of HEU Jemima plates and varying thicknesses of polyethylene. Additionally, one fast unmoderated configuration was reflected on top and bottom by the hafnium plates [6]. Because the dominant fission spectra changed significantly across the five measurements, this benchmark is cross listed with three additional identifiers to facilitate Handbook users in identification of experiments requisite to their specific needs.

HEU-MET-MIXED-021 (also cross listed as HEU-MET-FAST-103, HEU-MET-INTER-012, and HEU-MET-THERM-036): The TEX-HEU baseline experiments were performed using HEU Jemima plates and varying thicknesses of interstitial polyethylene to tune the neutron fission spectra from fast to thermal [2]. Because the dominant fission spectra changed significantly across the five measurements, this benchmark is cross listed with three additional identifiers to facilitate Handbook users in identification of experiments requisite to their specific needs. TEX is a collaboration between LLNL and LANL and the experiments were conducted on the Comet machine at NCERC.

2.3. New Intermediate Enriched Uranium Evaluations

IEU-MET-FAST-025: This experiment was a collaboration between JAEA and LANL to test the void reactivity worth for lead for fast reactors. The experiments used a mixture of HEU and natural uranium plates (targeting an intermediate uranium enrichment) with interstitial lead stacked inside the Zeus copper reflector on the Comet vertical assembly machine [4]. Four experiments were evaluated, one being a reference configuration and the other three with increasing lead void via the implementation of aluminum spacers.

2.4. New Low Enriched Uranium Evaluations

Two new evaluations published in ICSBEP used Low Enriched Uranium (LEU) as the fissile material. Overviews of the new LEU evaluations are provided, below.

LEU-COMP-THERM-110: The Matériaux Interaction Réflexion Toutes Epaisseurs (MIRTE, translated into English as Materials, Interaction, Reflection, All Thickness) program was carried out between 2008 and 2013 at the Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique (CEA) Valduc Center in France [7]. The purpose of this program was to measure integral reactivity characteristics for various structural materials, providing benchmark validation data

for modern nuclear codes and data utilized in criticality safety and reactor physics applications. This benchmark contains six critical configurations in the third experimental MIRTE series and the Zircaloy-4-clad UO₂ (4.738 wt.%) rods were surrounded by steel or copper sleeves in either water or an aluminum block with varying degrees of moderation.

LEU-COMP-THERM-111: The experiments described in this benchmark were performed at the Sandia Critical Experiments Facility (SCXF) to test the effects of molybdenum sleeves in water-reflected, water-moderated, triangular-pitched lattices of UO₂ fuel (6.9 wt.% enriched ²³⁵U) [8]. Five benchmark configurations that varied in the number and placement of molybdenum sleeves around fuel rods were included.

2.5. New Alarm/Shielding Evaluations

ALARM-CF-CU-SHIELD-001: The neutron leakage flux through a copper block was evaluated across the energy range of 1.0 to 11.0 MeV using a ²⁵²Cf source to pass neutrons through a copper block. The experiment was a simple geometry integral experiment to support nuclear data testing [9]. The experiment was performed at the Research Centre Řež (RCR, Centrum výzkumu Řež) in Czechia.

ALARM-CF-NI-SHIELD-001 (also cross listed as ALARM-CF-FE-SHIELD-002): This evaluation benchmarks two neutron leakage measurements from a ²⁵²Cf source placed in the center of a 50 cm iron sphere and a similar nickel sphere [9]. The experiments were performed at RCR in Czechia.

ALARM-CF-SST-SHIELD-002: This evaluation benchmarks a neutron leakage measurement from a ²⁵²Cf source placed in the center of large stainless steel 321 (SS321) block [9]. The experiments were performed at RCR in Czechia.

2.6. New Fundamental Physics Evaluations

FUND-ORELA-ACC-GRAPH-PNSDT-001: An experiment was performed to benchmark slowing down characteristics of neutrons in nuclear graphite in the Oak Ridge Electron Linear Accelerator (ORELA) facility [10]. Neutron pulses from ORELA were injected into a rectangular reactor-grade graphite pile that approximated a 70 cm cube. The time-dependent reaction rate of neutrons from the graphite pile was counted by a lithium glass scintillation detector that was placed above the pile. The evaluation was completed by North Carolina State University (NCSSU).

FUND-LLNL-DT-PE-PNDA-001 (also cross listed as FUND-LLNL-DT-PE-PMMA-001): This evaluation benchmarked a series of pulsed-neutron die-away (PNDA) experiments completed at LLNL, with the goal of providing a validation for thermal neutron scattering laws. The experiment used a pulsed deuterium-tritium (D-T) neutron generator impinging on a moderating target. The neutrons scattered and thermalized within the target and were counted as a function of time using ³He detectors surrounding the target. These data provide a time-decay profile of the neutron population that can be fitted to a simple exponential decay equation, with the benchmark quantity being the decay constant from the exponent, α [11]. Four high density polyethylene (HDPE) and four PMMA (Lucite) targets were evaluated.

3. REVISED EVALUATIONS

The 2022/2023 and 2024 editions of the Handbook saw 3 major revisions to existing, approved benchmarks. Minor revisions to existing benchmark evaluations typically include rectifying minor errors such as incorrect information placed in figures, adding a needed clarification, or inclusion of information necessary to complete the benchmark evaluation that was accidentally excluded. Minor revisions do not significantly impact the final results of the benchmark evaluation itself. Major revisions impact the overall results or incur changes to the benchmark model description. Users of benchmarks are strongly encouraged to update their benchmark suite in light of a major revision. Significant revisions to benchmarks are detailed in Table II.

Table II. Details of Major Benchmark Revisions in the 2022/2023 and 2024 Editions

ICSBEP Identifier	Significant Revision Notes
PU-MET-MIXED-002	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision to expected benchmark values and benchmark uncertainties for detailed and simplified models. • Updated figures in Section 3 to correct typographical errors • Changed many instances of “weight fraction” and “weight percent” to “mass fraction” in tables and text. • Minor change to benchmark input files for the Y+/Y- dimension of aluminum fins that does not impact k_{eff} calculation. • SCALE Keno results and input files added.
PU-SOL-THERM-028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision of benchmark uncertainties to reflect revised solution chemistry uncertainties • Added additional information about measurements • No changes to benchmark models • Added many additional sample results for updated nuclear data libraries.
HEU-MET-FAST-028	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revision to expected benchmark values and benchmark uncertainties, addition of new detailed and simplified model. • Significant update to the benchmark geometry based on new measurements and data

4. PREPARATIONS FOR THE 2025 EDITION OF THE HANDBOOK

The ICSBEP TRG met at the Jožef Stefan Institute in Ljubljana, Slovenia, in April 2025 to review benchmarks for inclusion into the 2025 ICSBEP Handbook. Eight evaluations were finalized for inclusion into the 2025 Handbook, which will be published in the near future. The eight evaluations are briefly described, below:

PU-MET-FAST-047: This evaluation focuses on the first series of Jupiter experiments conducted with JAEA by LANL, which were configurations of plutonium ZPPR plates and interstitial lead plates arranged in boxes reflected by the Zeus copper reflector [12]. Like previous JAEA/LANL experiments, the goal was to measure the lead void reactivity of the assembly.

PU-MET-FAST-050: This evaluation focuses on the second series of Jupiter experiments conducted with JAEA by LANL which saw the replacement of some of the Pu/Al ZPPR plates with plates that contained a higher fraction of ^{240}Pu [13]. Like previous experiments, the goal was to measure the lead void reactivity of the assembly.

HEU-MET-FAST-106: The LANL Critical Experiment Reflected by Copper to Better Understand Scattering (CERBERUS) series of experiments used HEU Jemima plates stacked with interstitial copper surrounded by the Zeus copper reflector, measured on Comet at NCERC [14]. The experiment was designed to provide a validation case to test copper neutron scattering cross sections and the benchmark presented three cases that vary on the thickness of interstitial copper between HEU layers.

HEU-MET-THERM-038 (also cross listed as HEU-MET-INTER-014): This benchmark evaluated the third in the series of TEX-HEU experiments, a collaboration between LLNL and LANL with experiments conducted on the Comet machine at NCERC. The TEX-CI assemblies used the HEU Jemima plates stacked with varying levels of polyethylene moderator and plates filled with packed sodium chloride salt. The motivation for the experiments was to provide validation cases for chlorine absorption for electrorefining operations and molten salt fuel forms [15].

LEU-COMP-THERM-112: The experiments described in this benchmark were performed at SCXF to test the effects of tantalum rods in a central test region driven by a water-reflected, water-moderated, triangular-pitched lattices of UO_2 fuel (6.9 wt.% enriched ^{235}U). The experiments were a collaboration between Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) and Sandia and were designed to achieve significant sensitivity to tantalum neutron capture in the epithermal/intermediate energy range [16].

ALARM-CF-PTFE-SHIELD-001: This evaluation benchmarks a neutron leakage measurement from a ^{252}Cf source placed in the center of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE, or Teflon) block. Activation foils were placed at various depths inside the PTFE block, and the leakage spectrum was measured using the proton recoil method [9]. The motivation for the measurements was to study neutron scattering in fluorine, particularly due to the usage of FLiNa and FLiBe salts in various nuclear applications and UF_6 being very important for uranium enrichment. The experiment was performed at the RCR in Czechia.

ALARM-CF-AL-SHIELD-001: This evaluation benchmarks a neutron leakage measurement from a ^{252}Cf source placed in the center of an aluminum block. Activation foils were placed at various depths inside the block, and the leakage spectrum was measured using the proton recoil method [9]. The motivation for the measurements was to study neutron scattering in aluminum due to its wide usage in the nuclear industry as an important structural component. The experiment was performed at the RCR in Czechia.

FUND-LLNL-DT-H2O-PNDA: This fundamental physics evaluation benchmarked the second series PNDA experiments completed at LLNL, with the goal of providing a validation for thermal neutron scattering laws [11]. Four light water targets were evaluated.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The ICSBEP continues to deliver high-quality, peer reviewed evaluations of experiments relevant to the nuclear criticality safety, reactor physics, and nuclear data communities. As seen in the recently published and soon-to-be-published ICSBEP edition content, the last decade has seen a renewed interest in benchmarking new integral experiments and the ICSBEP content has shifted from evaluations of historical experiments to contemporaneous benchmarking of recently completed experiments. Additionally, many of the new experiments included in the Handbook have been specifically designed to target long-standing validation gaps applicable to advanced reactor design, which will need validation cases for new fuel forms (like molten salts), non-traditional moderators, and energy spectra outside of the traditional light water reactor thermal spectrum. The ICSBEP TRG plans to meet in April of 2026 to review new candidate benchmark evaluations for inclusion into the handbook. A number of the in-development evaluations planned for review at future TRG meetings will also be applicable to advanced reactors, including experimental benchmarks of systems containing high assay low enriched uranium (HALEU) and tri-structural isotropic (TRISO) particle fuel.

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